

**TIL, TA'LIM, TARJIMA
ЯЗЫК, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ПЕРЕВОД
LANGUAGE, EDUCATION, TRANSLATION**

ТА'LIM

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**CLUSTER APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH TO SENIOR SCHOOL
STUDENTS**

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problem of applying the cluster approach to the educational process of high school students by the example of their teaching English. The article substantiates that the cluster approach in education makes it possible to act effectively and successfully, bearing in mind the priority perspective common to all partners, it is advisable to coordinate joint educational activities. It is this type of activity that makes it possible to provide more effective assistance to community members who participate in the partnership, to rationally approach its use, to ensure that they remain unlike each other, to recognize the differences and the importance of the role of individuals and organizations.

Keywords: cluster; cluster approach; English; method; technique; pragmalinguistics; sector.

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**MAKTABDAGI KATTA SINIF O'QUVCHILARIGA INGLIZ TILINI
KLASTER YONDASHUVI ORQALI O'QITISH**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola maktab katta sinf o'quvchilarini ingliz tiliga o'rgatish ta'lim jarayon misolida klasterli yondashuvni qo'llash muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada ta'limda klaster yondashuvi barcha klasterning barcha hamkor a'zolari uchun umumiy bo'lgan ustuvor istiqbollari hisobga olinsa, yanada samarali va muvaffaqiyatli harakat qilish imkonini berishi haqiqatni asoslaydi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada birgalikda ta'lim faoliyatini olib borish muvofiqligi ta'kidlangan. Bu hamjamiyat a'zolariga katta muvaffaqiyatlarga erishish, natijalardan oqilona yondashish, o'xshashlik bo'lmagan taqdirda o'ziga xoslikka erishish, jarayondagi individual ishtirokchilarning rolini tan olish va hurmat qilish imkonini beradigan birgalikdagi faoliyatdir.

Kalit so'zlar: klaster; klaster yondashuv; ingliz tili; usul; texnika; pragmalinqvistika; sektor.

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КЛАСТЕРНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБУЧЕНИЮ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ УЧАЩИХСЯ СТАРШИХ КЛАССОВ ШКОЛ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена проблеме применения кластерного подхода в образовательный процесс учащихся старших классов школ на примере их обучения английскому языку. В статье обосновывается то, что кластерный подход в образовании позволяет действовать эффективно и успешно, имея в виду приоритетную перспективу, общую для всех партнеров, целесообразно координировать совместную образовательную деятельность. Именно такой вид деятельности даёт возможность оказывать более эффективную помощь членам сообщества, которые участвуют в партнёрстве, рационально подходить к его использованию, добиваться того, чтобы, оставаясь непохожими друг на друга, признавать различия и важность роли отдельных людей и организаций.

Ключевые слова: кластер; кластерный подход; английский язык; метод; приём; прагмалингвистика; сектор.

Introduction. Any state in the world strives to create an education system that allows students to be in demand after graduation both within their own country and abroad. Therefore, with regard to the education system, the primary task of the state is to perform functions that are not available to other participants in the educational process, such as financing, providing tax benefits and using other mechanisms to

stimulate the educational services market, in order to train specialists qualified in the most promising fields of knowledge through licensing and certification. In such a situation, “partnership mechanisms will act as a kind of regulator of the opinions and interests of all participants in this process” [1, 104]. But the process of implementing partnership mechanisms in the field of education will be complicated by some negative factors associated with the unwillingness of educational organizations to introduce partnership into the structure of the institution's activities. One of the ways out of the current situation may be the use of a cluster approach in achieving the goals of the development of education, which assumes mutually beneficial, continuity, cooperation, mutual participation.

The scenario of long-term development of the country assumes the growth of its competitiveness in both traditional and new knowledge-intensive sectors, a breakthrough in improving the quality of human capital and labor productivity dynamics, in the advanced development of high-tech industries and the transformation of innovative factors into the main source of economic growth [2, 34]. The solution of these tasks will require the creation of a system of clear interaction between the state, business, science and education based on the use of effective innovative development tools, among which the cluster approach should play an important role [3, 16]. The idea of increasing the competitiveness of the national economy based on the implementation of cluster strategies is not new. But at the present stage, when traditional methods of diversification can no longer give proper returns, the use of a cluster model has no alternative. The interdependence and interrelationships between the processes of clustering, strengthening competitiveness and accelerating innovation is a new phenomenon that allows us to resist the onslaught of global competition and properly meet the requirements of national and international development.

Research methodology. As part of the organization and conduct of this theoretical research, the following methods were used: analysis of scientific and educational literature on the research problem (taking notes, annotating, quoting, extracts); analysis of regulatory sources on the selected problem; study and analysis of programs and program documents in the field of education.

The Results of the Study. Currently, the problem of teaching a foreign language at school is extremely urgent. All teachers of a foreign language in the Republic of Uzbekistan are faced with the task of forming a personality that will not only possess language skills and knowledge, but will also be able to freely participate in intercultural communication at a high level. In the field of teaching a foreign language, it is very important to form a communicative competence that includes both linguistic and socio-cultural competence. This feature – knowledge of the socio-cultural background is very significant, because without it is impossible to form a communicative competence even within limited limits. Therefore, it is necessary to have an idea of the socio-cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied. In addition, teachers of a foreign language (in our case,

English) are faced with the task of forming positive motivation, it is necessary to link it with the cognitive interests of students, the need to acquire new knowledge, skills, and skills. This is the point of contact with such a concept as "cluster".

The problem for the most part lies in the educational institutions themselves, which are trapped because of the outdated approach to creating an educational product (service) that has developed historically. They still view the creation of an educational product (service) narrowly, limiting themselves to achieving short-term success, missing the most important additional competencies in demand in the regional labor market, and do not pay attention to the broader influential forces of the innovative economy that determine long-term success. Universities should take the initiative and ensure a unified approach of the educational community and business to the creation of an innovative combined educational product. The combined innovative educational product requires the use of convergent technologies based on the combination of competencies from different fields of scientific knowledge. Therefore, educational programs should be constantly improved, taking into account the innovative needs of enterprises. Shared educational values are not social responsibility or even the sustainability of the educational community, but a new way to achieve economic success.

The needs for quality education determine the labor markets, and the cumulative educational products may cause internal additional costs for educational institutions due to the need to introduce corrective training [4, 121]. The state, for its part, trying to regulate this problem through the improvement of educational standards, believes that business should bear the costs associated with compensating for deficiencies in education. Business resists such approaches, which invariably contradict its interests. Indirectly, each party believes that the other party is an obstacle to achieving the goals, and acts accordingly. Meanwhile, the participation of businesses in corrective training does not necessarily increase their costs, because they, receiving highly qualified personnel, can innovate through the use of new technologies, working methods, management approaches, increase labor productivity and expand their markets [5, 22]. And then it turns out that innovative cumulative educational values are not personal values. The prospect of creating aggregate value is aimed at improving the technology of cultivation and strengthening the regional forest educational cluster and all its participants in order to increase efficiency, concentration and optimization of resources, labor productivity, quality and sustainability.

Let's consider this issue in more detail from the point of view of teaching English to high school students. It is known that those who study a foreign language should have good communication skills. In order to stimulate the development of these skills, it is necessary to choose such forms of the lesson that will most contribute to this. Research and experience of innovative teachers have shown that in order to maintain fruitful and effective activity of students, the use of non-traditional forms of classes is successful, for example, such as a video lesson, a

discussion lesson, a performance lesson, an excursion lesson, etc. [6; 7; 8] The fact is that such forms of classes support students' interest in the subject and they increase motivation to study. During such lessons, students' horizons expand, plus with an increase in information about the culture of the country, the language being studied, the socio-cultural competence of students improves. Why do we say that it is necessary to apply these teaching methods? The fact is that during, for example, a video lesson, students are introduced to the culture of the countries of the language being studied by immersing them in the atmosphere of native speakers' relationships with a demonstration of the peculiarities of their facial expressions and gestures.

The English lesson has its own specifics, which the English teacher cannot ignore. Currently, the global goal of mastering English is considered to be familiarization with another culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved by developing the ability for intercultural communication. It is teaching, organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of the English lesson.

Foreign language communication is based on the theory of speech activity. Communicative English language teaching is of an activity nature, since speech communication is carried out through "speech activity", which, in turn, serves to solve the tasks of productive human activity in the conditions of "social interaction" of communicating people. Participants of communication try to solve real and imaginary tasks of joint activity with the help of a foreign language.

The activity-based essence of communicative-oriented teaching of a foreign language is realized in the conditions of a cluster approach to learning. With this approach, positive conditions are created for the active and free development of personality in activity. In general, these conditions boil down to the following: students get the opportunity to freely express their thoughts and feelings in the process of communication; each participant in communication remains in the focus of attention of others; participants in communication feel safe from criticism, persecution for mistakes and punishment.

With a cluster approach to learning, cognitive barriers – characteristic of the educational process – disappear, reducing the motivation of students, encouraging them to irritability [9, 25].

The cluster approach involves student-centered learning [10, 47]. This means that teaching, or rather, interacting students are the center of cognitive activity in the classroom. Summing up the above, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of interaction and cooperation of students, as well as speech tasks for the organization of communicative language acquisition. Communicative learning involves the formation of a communicative concept, that is, internal readiness and ability for verbal communication, orienting students to "enter" another cultural space. Such training is characterized, first of all, by non-traditional forms of conducting classes.

Discussion of the Results. Based on the data of pragmalinguistics and taking into account the changed status of a foreign language as a means of communication and mutual understanding in the world community, all the psychological features of teaching a foreign language to high school students are grouped around the need to strengthen the pragmatic aspects of language learning. This means that during training, it will be important not only to achieve high-quality results in mastering foreign language communication, but also to find a real way out to a different culture and its carriers.

It is not just about knowledge of the language, but about the ability to use it in real communication, i.e. about practical command of the language and, consequently, about the development of "pragmatic intercultural competence".

The state standard of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign languages notes that the formation of communicative competence is inextricably linked with socio-cultural and regional knowledge, in other words, as if with "secondary socialization". Without knowledge of the socio-cultural background, it is impossible to form a communicative competence even within limited limits. In this regard, it is necessary to adhere to the principle: only culture in its various manifestations contributes to the formation of a person's personality.

We will justify the choice of these aspects:

1. At the present difficult time, pragmatic human needs come to the fore. Regarding the teaching of a foreign language, this has the following refraction: socio-cultural and regional knowledge is able to satisfy pragmalinguistic needs, such as the possibility of traveling abroad, etc. - a very powerful psychological factor in teaching foreign languages.

2. The motivational aspect is also crucial for the activation of all psychological processes – thinking, perception, understanding and assimilation of foreign language material. To do this, it is necessary to increase motivation levels, contributing to the development of cognition and intellectual activity among students, aiming ultimately to increase the effectiveness of the learning process.

The choice of the senior school age is due to the fact that high school students in many ways can be considered already formed and mature personalities, so when discussing this age, in many ways you can "not make allowances for childhood", but consider the personality in all its versatility [11, 34].

The modern school faces tasks related to creating conditions for the intellectual and spiritual and moral development of students, for the preparation of an intelligent person; for educating in each student the need for self-education, self-education and self-development; for the formation of a broad and humane view of the world among students.

The system of regular and extracurricular work at school in all academic disciplines should be aimed at solving these tasks.

Foreign language is an activity-based educational subject that has educational, educational and developmental potential, creating a solid foundation for the formation of an intelligent person.

In order to ensure the continuity of language education, the secondary school provides students who have completed the basic course of study in grade 9 with the opportunity to continue learning English at the senior stage (grades 10-11).

Let us consider the characteristic features of teaching English at the senior stage. According to the materials of the collection containing a set of software and regulatory documents for grades 10-11, these are:

1) more active interaction of all types of speech activity (reading, speaking, listening, writing);

2) the use of authentic, problematic journalistic and artistic texts as sources of information concerning current topics of our time;

3) great initiative and spontaneity of students' speech, in which non-standard communication situations may be affected;

4) the main types of dialogic speech – free conversation, group discussion of the proposed problem, the predominance of dialogue – exchange of views;

5) the construction of detailed own statements based on the text and independently, with sufficient argumentation about what was read or heard.

Thus, the main purpose of teaching English at the senior stage is to improve all components of foreign language communicative competence, which is the main condition for the implementation of intercultural communication in general.

At the final stage of training, it is advisable to use such a pedagogical technology that would enable the teacher to introduce his students into the process of cognition, to focus them on the search for knowledge, that is, it would contribute to the further development of the secondary linguistic personality and the improvement of the primary, further formation of communicative, socio-cultural and intercultural competence.

Conclusion. So, in this study, we found out that currently the problem of teaching English at school is relevant. English language teachers are faced with the task of forming a personality that will be able to participate in intercultural communication. The English lesson has its own specifics, which the English teacher cannot ignore. Currently, the global goal of mastering English is considered to be familiarization with another culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. It is not just about knowledge of the language, but about the ability to use it in real communication, i.e. on practical language proficiency. We chose the senior school age, because high school students in many ways can be considered already formed and mature personalities, thus, when discussing this age, in many ways it is possible "not to make allowances for childhood", but to consider the personality in all its versatility. We talked about the specifics of teaching English in high school and concluded that the main goal of teaching English at the senior stage is to improve all components of foreign language communicative competence, which is the main

condition for the implementation of intercultural communication in general. If we take into account the research of the first chapter, we can conclude that the use of the methodology with the use of video at this stage of training can be very effective.

The shift of emphasis from the traditional lesson, burdened in recent decades in pedagogy by increasing homework, to the development of alternative forms of educational activity will contribute, in our opinion, to a more constructive transition to new educational standards. Project activities, dives, educational trips, workshops, parent lessons, on the one hand, will help to diversify the child's life, on the other hand, will increase the teacher's opportunities for self-realization.

The application of the cluster approach in high school in the process of teaching English will require the school itself to develop its own infrastructure, search for additional resources both inside and outside. At the same time, the cluster approach is a kind of safety cushion for the school. The most effective development of the cluster approach, which means that the cluster model of building a school will be able to be implemented in the case of optimizing the ratio of the invariant, variable and additional parts of the basic standard. In our view, the variable and additional parts should expand along with the increase in the degree of voluntary educational activity. It seems to us that the era of compulsory education is gradually coming to an end. Along with the increase in the availability of education, its variability, freedom of access to information, the child's interest in learning should also grow, which by definition cannot be formed by violent methods (the maximum that such methods are capable of is to cause an imitation of interest, which disappears with the weakening of external pressure). Apparently, the future belongs to the self-education of a person, but not individual, but in organized creative forms, in interest groups, where there is a psychological feeding of each other by people whose aspirations are similar. Any school has the basics of cluster interaction today. The role of the state, in our opinion, is to maximize the support of this type of relationship in the school, encourage points of its development and provide this direction with a green corridor.

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